

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17624114

Evaluating the Effectiveness of the United Nations' Universal Periodic Review in Promoting the Right to Life and Fair Trial in South-East Nigeria

Aideloje, Sunday; Prof. B.O.G. Nwanolue & Prof. Charles A. Obiora

Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Human rights is considered human privileges and entitlements for being human. Despite the presence of both constitutional and international human rights frameworks, violations remain pervasive in South-East Nigeria. Between 2015 and 2023, the region experienced widespread reports of arbitrary killings, unlawful detentions, enforced disappearances, torture, arising from state security operations and activities of separatist groups. These violations were often accompanied by limited access to justice, prolonged pre-trial detentions, and systemic erosion of due process. The study evaluates the effectiveness of the United Nations' Universal Periodic Review in Promoting the Right to Life and Fair Trial in South-East Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined how the United Nations' Universal Periodic Review (UPR) has influenced compliance with the Right to Life and the Right to Fair Trial in South-East Nigeria. Identified the challenges limiting the effectiveness of the UN in promoting human rights in South-East Nigeria and proposed strategies for strengthening collaboration between the UN and Nigerian institutions, such as the NHRC and NCAT, to enhance the protection of the Right to Life and the Right to Fair Trial in South-East Nigeria. This study is anchored Human Rights Theory which can be traced to classical and Enlightenment philosophers such as John Locke (1690), Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1762), and Immanuel Kant (1785), whose writings collectively shaped modern conceptions of liberty, justice, and human dignity. The analysis is conducted thematically and qualitatively. The study reveals that United Nations has significantly contributed to raising awareness and promoting discourse on human rights in South-East Nigeria, the tangible outcomes of its interventions remain limited. Persistent Human Rights Violations Despite International Engagement. Weak Institutional Enforcement and Capacity Deficits. Low Implementation of UPR Recommendations. Security-Oriented Governance and Rights Abuses. Fragmented UN-Civil Society Partnerships. Partial Effectiveness of UN Interventions. The study concludes that while the United Nations has made commendable efforts to promote human rights in South-East Nigeria, its influence has been primarily normative rather than transformative. The persistence of violations of the Right to Life and the Right to Fair Trial underscores the limitations of international engagement in contexts where domestic institutions are weak and political will is low. Amongst the recommendations is that sustainable human rights improvement in South-East Nigeria will depend on strengthened judicial independence, empowered national institutions such as the NHRC and NCAT, and transparent oversight of security agencies. Active civil society participation and continuous engagement with international partners are vital to sustaining reform momentum. Achieving durable progress requires collective action by state institutions, civil society, and citizens to institutionalize the principles of justice, equality, and respect for human dignity in both law and practice.

Keywords: United Nations' Universal Periodic Review, Right to Life, Fair Trial, South-East, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the promotion of human rights is recognized as the foundation of freedom, justice, and an indispensable element in preserving world peace and security (Dada, 2013). The concept of human rights has existed for millennia, with its roots traceable to early philosophical writings such as Thomas Hobbes' notion of the '*state of nature*'. Hobbes (1651) argued that in the absence of organized institutions, human life was "solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short," with individuals

driven by egoism and self-interest. The social contract, according to Hobbes, was therefore necessary to create the state, establish laws, regulate human conduct, and protect human rights from arbitrary human behavior.

Subsequent thinkers, including Locke (1690), Rousseau (1762), and Kant (1785), laid the philosophical foundations for universal and inalienable human rights, emphasizing life, liberty, moral dignity, and collective responsibility of the state. Idigo, (2024) and Lauren (2011) link the contemporary human rights struggle to the emergence of natural law theories, Enlightenment philosophy, and social reforms spanning the 17th to 19th centuries including the French and American revolutions, abolitionist movements, women's suffrage campaigns, and labour rights activism.

In the 20th century, the quest for human rights protection became globally institutionalized, particularly through the formation of new states, development of governance structures, and establishment of international legal frameworks (Idigo, 2025). Colonial legacies, as described by Achebe (1983), imposed systemic oppression, forced labour, racial discrimination, and violations of human dignity, which undermined societal stability and human security. The impact of global conflicts, including World Wars I and II, further highlighted the need for coordinated international efforts to safeguard human rights. The failure of the League of Nations to prevent global conflict underscored the necessity of a stronger international institution, leading to the formation of the United Nations (UN) in 1945 and the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) in 1948 (United Nations Human Rights Office of the Commissioner, 2023).

The UDHR codified fundamental human rights into international law, establishing rights to life, liberty, security, fair hearing, property, education, and freedom from slavery, torture, and arbitrary detention (United Nations, 2023). Despite these global frameworks, human rights violations persisted throughout the 20th century, particularly under authoritarian regimes such as Nazism, Fascism, Soviet Totalitarianism, and military governments in countries including Nigeria, Argentina, Greece, and Chile (Idigo, 2022).

In Nigeria, democracy was reintroduced on May 29, 1999, promising the protection of fundamental human rights. However, violations have remained prevalent, often perpetrated by political actors and security agencies. Reports from Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch, and Transparency International document incidents of extrajudicial killings, unlawful detentions, torture, suppression of peaceful assembly, and restrictions on freedom of expression (Amnesty International, 2022; Human Rights Watch, 2021). Notable examples include the #EndSARS protests of October 2020, which were met with unlawful detention, killings of civilians, and suppression of journalists and activists.

Nigeria became a member of the **United Nations in 1960**, signaling its commitment to international human rights standards. The 1999 Constitution enshrines fundamental rights including the right to life, personal liberty, and fair hearing while national institutions such as the **National Human Rights Commission (NHRC)** and the **National Council on the Administration of Justice (NCAT)** are mandated to monitor and address human rights violations. Yet, despite these frameworks, practical enforcement remains weak, particularly in regions affected by insecurity, separatist movements, and political unrest.

Between **2015 and 2023**, South-East Nigeria experienced heightened human rights concerns due to separatist agitations, military operations, and civil unrest. Reports of **extrajudicial killings, arbitrary arrests, enforced disappearances, torture, and prolonged detentions without trial** raised serious questions about the protection of the **Right to Life** and the **Right to Fair Trial**. While the government often justifies such actions on the grounds of national security, the **use of excessive force and erosion of due process** remains a significant concern.

The **United Nations**, through mechanisms such as the **Universal Periodic Review (UPR)**, collaborates with domestic institutions like the NHRC and NCAT to promote compliance with international human rights standards. These efforts include **monitoring, advocacy, technical assistance, and support for dialogue** between government actors and civil society. However, persistent challenges such as political interference, weak institutional capacity, lack of transparency, and limited cooperation from state agencies continue to undermine effectiveness.

The **2015–2023 period** is particularly significant for this study, coinciding with intensified military operations in the South-East, rising civil unrest, and growing international concern regarding Nigeria's human rights record. By focusing on **South-East Nigeria** and two specific rights the **Right**

to Life and the Right to Fair Trial this study provides a **context-based analysis** of how the UN and domestic institutions interact to promote human rights protection and accountability.

This research seeks to critically evaluate the **role, effectiveness, and challenges of the UN**, in collaboration with Nigerian human rights institutions, in safeguarding fundamental rights in South-East Nigeria, thereby identifying gaps and proposing strategies for improved compliance and protection.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the presence of both constitutional and international human rights frameworks, violations remain pervasive in South-East Nigeria. Between 2015 and 2023, the region experienced widespread reports of arbitrary killings, unlawful detentions, enforced disappearances, and torture, arising from state security operations and activities of separatist groups (Amnesty International, 2022; Human Rights Watch, 2021). These violations were often accompanied by limited access to justice, prolonged pre-trial detentions, and systemic erosion of due process (Adebisi, Oyedeji, & Azeez, 2016).

While the United Nations, through mechanisms such as the Universal Periodic Review (UPR), collaborates with domestic institutions including the NHRC and NCAT to promote human rights compliance, challenges persist. Weak institutional capacity, political interference, inadequate coordination between domestic and international actors, and poor implementation of UN recommendations have significantly constrained the effectiveness of these interventions (United Nations Human Rights Office of the Commissioner, 2023; Dada, 2013).

These gaps raise critical concerns about the actual impact of the UN's diplomatic interventions on human rights protection in the region, particularly regarding the right to life and the right to fair trial. Consequently, this study leverages the problem of persistent human rights violations in South-East Nigeria despite existing international and national mechanisms for protection and accountability.

Review Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Human Rights

The idea of human rights founded on the concept of the innate dignity of all people is an essentially bold conviction that human nature tends to transcend its innate weaknesses and raise the level of moral consciousness to abstract values (Musiał-Kidawa, 2021). The notion of 'Human Rights' has roots tracing back to ancient times, finding prominence in India's legal discourse and gaining traction as a cornerstone of European culture, particularly democracy. Human rights, essentially fundamental and intrinsic to every individual's existence, were initially referred to as 'the rights of man' and are grounded on the belief that all humans inherently possess certain inalienable rights simply by virtue of their humanity (Nino, 1994). Regardless of factors such as race, gender, or social status, individuals universally hold these rights, as affirmed by the United States Declaration of Independence in 1776 and formally acknowledged in 1948 through the Universal Declaration of Human Rights by the United Nations General Assembly in Paris.

The terminology surrounding human rights extends to various labels such as 'Fundamental Rights', 'Basic Rights', 'Natural Rights', or 'Birth Rights', encapsulating a spectrum of rights including 'Civil Rights', 'Civil Liberties', and 'Social, Economic and Cultural Rights'. Central to the concept of human rights is the notion of human dignity, where rights essential for upholding human dignity are termed as such (Chandra, 1999). This sentiment is echoed in the preamble and Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, emphasizing the inherent dignity and equality of all individuals, underscoring the connection between human rights and natural law. Identifying four core features of human rights, they are recognized as rights, diverse, universal, and possessing high-priority (Nickel, 2019). These rights encompass freedoms, protections, statuses, or benefits for the rights holders (Beitz, 2009). Additionally, considerations may arise regarding their inalienability, political function, or imposition of moral obligations, expanding the discourse surrounding human rights beyond the foundational features outlined above.

In spite of the various meaningful and unique definitional attempts of human rights by scholars and institutions across the globe, there has been no general consensus. Even, United Nations definitions of the term had often been criticized by scholars. Nevertheless, however, the major fact that runs all through the reviewed definition is that human rights depict privileges or enjoyments that every individual is entitled to by the virtue of human existence.

The Application of International Human Rights Law in Nigeria: The Mandate of the UDHR and Related Instruments.

The Nigerian constitutional guarantees of the right to life and fair hearing are reinforced by international human rights instruments, most notably the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966) Article 3 of the UDHR provides that “everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person,” while Article 10 guarantees that “everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal.” These provisions collectively define the core standards of civil and political liberties globally (United Nations, 1948).

The ICCPR, which Nigeria ratified in 1993, elaborates further in Article 6 on the right to life and in Article 14 on the right to a fair and public hearing. These obligations require states to ensure the protection of life, prevent arbitrary deprivation of life, and maintain independent judicial mechanisms for the enforcement of rights (UN General Assembly, 1966). By ratifying these instruments, Nigeria undertook international legal obligations to promote and protect these rights within its territory.

Under Section 12(1) of the 1999 Constitution, international treaties ratified by Nigeria do not automatically have the force of law domestically until enacted by the National Assembly. Nonetheless, Nigerian courts have occasionally drawn upon international human rights treaties and conventions to interpret constitutional rights, especially where such treaties align with constitutional principles (*Abacha v. Fawehinmi* [2000] 6 NWLR (Pt. 660) 228). This interpretive approach reflects Nigeria’s commitment to harmonizing domestic law with international human rights standards (Agaba, 2019).

The United Nations plays a central role in promoting compliance with these global norms through various mechanisms, including the Universal Periodic Review (UPR), the Human Rights Council, and the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). These mechanisms assess the extent to which member states like Nigeria respect and implement international human rights obligations (Amnesty International, 2022). Nigeria’s engagements with the UPR process have produced several recommendations emphasizing the need to curb extrajudicial killings, strengthen the independence of the judiciary, and improve fair hearing guarantees (UN Human Rights Council, 2023).

UN Diplomatic Engagement on Human Right Issues in the South-East Nigeria

The United Nations (UN) diplomatic interventions in Nigeria provides essential context for understanding its evolving engagement with human rights issues, particularly in the South-East geopolitical zone. The South-East, comprising Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States, has been a flashpoint of human rights concerns, rooted in historical marginalization, political exclusion, and security repression. The UN’s interventions, though initially indirect, have gradually assumed a more structured diplomatic and institutional character, reflecting Nigeria’s international human rights obligations under the UN Charter, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966), and the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (1981).

This section traces the evolution of the UN’s diplomatic engagement in South-East Nigeria from the post-civil war era to the present, highlighting phases of institutional partnership, normative advocacy, and human rights monitoring between 2015 and 2023. It situates the South-East within Nigeria’s broader human rights context, emphasizing the UN’s role in shaping domestic accountability mechanisms such as the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), the National Committee Against Torture (NCAT), and other legal reforms.

Following the Nigerian Civil War (1967–1970), the UN maintained a delicate diplomatic posture that respected Nigeria’s sovereignty while promoting humanitarian rehabilitation in the war-torn South-East. Agencies such as the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF), the World Health Organization (WHO), and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) played crucial roles in post-war reconstruction, particularly in health, education, and community reintegration (Okafor, 2014). However, direct UN advocacy for human rights protection remained limited, largely due to Nigeria’s sensitivity to external interference and the prevailing international norm of non-intervention during internal conflicts.

By the late 1970s and 1980s, UN engagement in Nigeria became increasingly framed around **development diplomacy** linking socio-economic rights to political stability. The South-East benefited

modestly from UN-sponsored community development programs and governance reform initiatives aimed at rebuilding trust between the citizenry and state institutions (Ohaeri, 2020). Nonetheless, structural injustices, poor governance, and weak institutional accountability continued to fuel grievances across the region.

Renewed Diplomatic Engagement (2015–2023)

The period between 2015 and 2023 marks the most visible and sustained UN diplomatic engagement in South-East Nigeria. This era coincided with increased reports of human rights violations arising from separatist agitations, security operations, and the activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). International attention intensified following numerous reports of extrajudicial killings and arbitrary detentions by Nigerian security forces (Amnesty International, 2025).

In response, the UN's Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) increased its monitoring through periodic reports, statements, and engagements with the Nigerian government. The Universal Periodic Review (UPR) processes of 2013, 2018, and 2023 repeatedly raised concerns about excessive use of force in the South-East, urging Nigeria to investigate abuses and ensure accountability (United Nations Human Rights Council [UNHRC], 2023).

At the domestic level, the NHRC and OHCHR collaborated to strengthen complaint mechanisms. In 2022, the Commission launched a national call center and short code with UN support, enabling citizens to report violations directly (United Nations Nigeria, 2022). These interventions were part of the UN's broader preventive diplomacy using advocacy, technical assistance, and reporting to deter further violations.

2.3.2 Key Incidents Shaping UN Diplomacy in the South-East

Several incidents between 2015 and 2023 reinforced the urgency of UN diplomatic attention. The Onitsha protest killings of 2015 and 2016, where security forces reportedly opened fire on IPOB demonstrators, drew sharp condemnation from human rights bodies and international organizations. Amnesty International's findings (2016) identified excessive use of lethal force, torture, and mass arrests, prompting UN calls for independent investigations (Amnesty International, 2016).

Similarly, the Nsukka student killings in 2017 and the Awo-Omamma massacre in Imo State in 2022 further highlighted the breakdown of accountability. The UN and NHRC issued joint statements urging due process, emphasizing that the right to life and fair trial are non-derogable under international law (NHRC, 2022). Despite these efforts, most cases remain unresolved, illustrating the gap between diplomatic advocacy and enforcement.

Diplomatic Limitations and Structural Challenges

While the UN's diplomatic posture has enhanced human rights visibility in the South-East, its impact has been constrained by several factors. First, Nigeria's assertion of sovereignty limits external intervention, particularly where issues intersect with internal security. Second, weak state institutions and political resistance undermine the implementation of UN recommendations. Third, the multiplicity of actors—state, non-state, and armed groups—makes it difficult to ascribe accountability.

Furthermore, local human rights offices often lack adequate funding, personnel, and logistical support to sustain follow-up action on reported abuses. As a result, UN diplomatic efforts have achieved **normative progress**—raising awareness, establishing frameworks, and facilitating dialogue—but have not yet translated into consistent justice outcomes across the South-East (Ojukwu, 2022).

Historically, the UN's diplomatic interventions in South-East Nigeria demonstrate an evolving pattern: from humanitarian engagement in the post-civil war era to structured institutional collaboration and preventive diplomacy in recent years. The region's persistent human rights crises centering on the right to life and fair trial underscore both the necessity and the limits of international diplomacy in the face of domestic political resistance.

The UN's continued engagement through the NHRC, OHCHR, UNDP, and related bodies reflects a sustained commitment to strengthening Nigeria's human rights infrastructure. However, the South-East experience reveals that without genuine political will and judicial independence, the normative frameworks established through UN diplomacy risk remaining largely symbolic.

The United Nations (UN) Regulations on Human Rights

The United Nations has nine different regulations on human rights. These regulations include: Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR) of 1948, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) of 1976, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) of 1976, Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (CERD) of

1969, Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) of 1981, Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT) of 1987, Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) of 1990, International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families of 2003, and Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) of 2008 (United Nations, 1948; United Nations, 1966; United Nations, 1966; United Nations, 1965; United Nations, 1979; United Nations, 1984; United Nations, 1989; United Nations, 1990; United Nations, 2006).

The first UN regulation on Human Rights was proclaimed in 1948 and adopted by the United Nations General Assembly. The extraordinary vision and resolve of the drafters produced a document that, for the first time, articulated the rights and freedoms to which every human being is equally and inalienably entitled. According to Onuoha (2004), the regulation is available in more than 360 languages, and the Declaration is the most translated document in the world a testament to its global nature and reach. It has become a yardstick by which we measure right and wrong. It provides a foundation for a just and decent future for all, and has given people everywhere a powerful tool in the fight against oppression, impunity and affronts to human dignity.

The Right to Life

The right to life is universally recognized as the most fundamental of all human rights, forming the bedrock upon which all other rights are built. Without life, the enjoyment of any other right becomes meaningless. Consequently, the protection of life is not only a moral imperative but also a legal and political obligation on the part of states and international organizations. It constitutes the cornerstone of international human rights law and national constitutional guarantees.

Conceptual and Philosophical Foundations

Philosophically, the right to life is grounded in the notion of human dignity the intrinsic worth of every person regardless of race, gender, nationality, or social status. Classical thinkers such as John Locke (1689) viewed life as a natural right that pre-exists the state and cannot be arbitrarily taken away. Locke argued that the primary purpose of government is the preservation of life, liberty, and property. Similarly, Thomas Hobbes in *Leviathan* (1651) emphasized the state's duty to protect citizens from violent death, which he considered the ultimate evil in the "state of nature." These early philosophical assertions later influenced modern legal frameworks and international conventions on human rights.

International Legal Framework on the Right to Life

At the global level, the right to life is enshrined in Article 3 of the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948)**, which states that "everyone has the right to life, liberty, and security of person." This provision laid the foundation for binding international treaties, most notably **Article 6(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966)**, which declares that "every human being has the inherent right to life. This right shall be protected by law. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his life." The ICCPR further obligates state parties to investigate, prevent, and punish violations of this right.

At the **regional level**, similar provisions are found in Article 4 of the **African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (1981)**, which provides that "human beings are inviolable. Every human being shall be entitled to respect for his life and the integrity of his person. No one may be arbitrarily deprived of this right." The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) has consistently interpreted this article broadly to include not only the prohibition of unlawful killings but also the duty of states to protect citizens from foreseeable threats to life, such as extrajudicial killings, poor prison conditions, and failure to prevent communal violence.

The Nigerian Constitutional Basis for the Right to Life

Domestically, the **1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended)** guarantees the right to life under **Section 33(1)**, which provides that "every person has a right to life, and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life, save in execution of the sentence of a court in respect of a criminal offence of which he has been found guilty." The provision further outlines exceptions under which life may be lawfully taken, such as self-defence, lawful arrest, and suppression of riots or insurrection.

However, while the constitutional provision appears robust, the reality in Nigeria especially in conflict-prone regions such as the South-East reveals systemic violations of this right. Security operations, insurgency, separatist agitation, and communal clashes have collectively contributed to

significant loss of lives. Reports from the **Nigeria Security Tracker (NST)** maintained by the Council on Foreign Relations (CFR) provide quantitative evidence of these violations.

Empirical Trends in Violations of the Right to Life (2015–2023)

Data from the **Nigeria Security Tracker (NST, 2023)** show that between **2015 and 2023**, more than **63,000 deaths** occurred in Nigeria from violent incidents involving state and non-state actors. Within the **South-East region**, comprising Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States, there was a marked increase in deaths linked to extrajudicial killings, clashes between separatist groups and security forces, and communal conflicts.

The Right to Fair Trial (Fair Hearing)

The right to fair trial, commonly referred to in Nigeria as the right to fair hearing, is a fundamental human right that ensures justice, equality, and due process in legal proceedings. It protects individuals from arbitrary deprivation of life, liberty, or property and guarantees that legal processes are conducted transparently, impartially, and without bias. The right to fair trial is essential because it provides the procedural framework through which other rights, such as the right to life and liberty, are protected (Stein, 2004). Philosophically, the concept is grounded in the natural law tradition, which emphasizes justice and equality as essential principles of governance. Classical thinkers, such as Aristotle and Cicero, recognized fairness as a core virtue, while John Locke argued that individuals surrender some freedoms to the state only under the condition that the state ensures protection of life, liberty, and property through lawful processes (Locke, 1689). Similarly, A.V. Dicey emphasized the rule of law, affirming that every individual, regardless of status, must be subject to the same legal procedures and entitled to impartial adjudication (Dicey, 1885).

Internationally, the right to fair trial is recognized under Articles 10 and 11 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948), which guarantees the right to a public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal. Article 14 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966) further details fair trial guarantees, including the presumption of innocence, timely notification of charges, adequate time and facilities to prepare a defense, legal counsel of choice, the right to examine witnesses, the right to a public trial, and the right to appeal. Regionally, Article 7 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (1981) affirms the right to be heard before competent national organs, presumed innocent until proven guilty, and defended by counsel of choice, while emphasizing the requirement of impartial tribunals. These provisions have been domesticated in Nigeria through Cap A9, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (2004), giving them legal force.

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria guarantees the right to fair hearing under Section 36. This section provides that in the determination of civil or criminal rights, individuals are entitled to a fair hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial tribunal. Subsections 4–12 provide further procedural safeguards, including the right to be informed promptly of charges, access to legal counsel, and protection against retrospective criminal laws and self-incrimination. The Supreme Court of Nigeria has reinforced this principle, holding that any legal proceeding that denies a party a fair hearing is null and void (*Ariori v. Elemo*, 1983; *Military Governor of Lagos State v. Ojukwu*, 1986).

Despite the constitutional and international protections, violations of the right to fair hearing in Nigeria, particularly in the South-East, remain widespread. These violations arise from weak judicial institutions, corruption, delayed trials, lack of access to legal representation, and excessive executive influence over the judiciary (Amnesty International, 2021; NHRC, 2022). Data from the Nigerian Correctional Service indicate that as of 2022, approximately 74% of inmates were awaiting trial, with South-East states such as Anambra and Imo recording pre-trial detention rates between 68% and 80% (Nigerian Correctional Service, 2023). Many detainees spend between three and ten years in custody without formal charges due to police inefficiency, prosecutorial delays, and congested courts. Human rights organizations have also reported cases of torture and coerced confessions in detention, particularly in counter-insurgency and anti-separatist operations (Amnesty International, 2022).

Gaps in Literature

A careful review of both international and Nigerian studies on human rights reveals several gaps that justify the need for this study:

1. **Geographical Gap:** Most empirical studies on UN interventions in Nigeria focus on the North-East, particularly in conflict-affected areas with insurgency. Very few studies

specifically examine the South-East, despite political agitations, security operations, and civil unrest that have led to human rights violations in the region.

2. **Thematic Gap:** Existing literature often addresses general human rights issues or broader international interventions. There is limited focus on specific rights, particularly the **Right to Life** and the **Right to Fair Trial**, within the South-East Nigerian context.
3. **Institutional Gap:** While studies emphasize the UN's role globally or in collaboration with Nigerian institutions, there is insufficient empirical analysis of **how the UN interacts with domestic bodies** such as the NHRC and NCAT to promote compliance with human rights standards in the South-East.
4. **Temporal Gap:** Few studies concentrate on the period **2015–2023**, which includes recent UPR cycles, increased international attention, and specific human rights challenges in the South-East.
5. **Effectiveness Gap:** Although several studies document human rights violations, there is a lack of rigorous evaluation regarding the **actual impact of UN mechanisms**, such as the UPR, in improving human rights outcomes in South-East Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored Human Rights Theory which is rooted in the enduring belief that every human being possesses inherent worth and dignity that must be respected and protected by all social and political institutions. The theory which is based on natural law, holds that some rights exist naturally and do not depend on the state for recognition. These rights are not granted by governments; rather, they are innate to the human condition. The intellectual foundations of Human Rights Theory can be traced to classical and Enlightenment philosophers such as John Locke (1690), Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1762), and Immanuel Kant (1785), whose writings collectively shaped modern conceptions of liberty, justice, and human dignity.

John Locke's *Second Treatise on Government* argued that individuals are born with natural rights to life, liberty, and property, and that the legitimacy of any government rests on its capacity to protect these rights. Rousseau's *Social Contract* reinterpreted this principle by emphasizing the moral and collective responsibility of the state to ensure justice and equality within the community. Immanuel Kant, in his *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals* (1785), went further to universalize the moral obligation to treat every human being as an end in themselves, never merely as a means to an end. This moral imperative, translated into political philosophy, became the foundation for universal human rights.

These philosophical underpinnings influenced the drafting of modern human rights instruments, notably the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (UDHR) in 1948, which proclaimed that "all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights." The UDHR established a universal moral code that transcends cultural and political boundaries, articulating the indivisibility, interdependence, and universality of human rights (United Nations, 1948; Donnelly, 2013). Subsequently, these ideals were codified into legally binding treaties, such as the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* (ICCPR, 1966) and the *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights* (ICESCR, 1966), creating a global normative order of rights and obligations.

At its core, Human Rights Theory posits that the protection of life and liberty is the primary purpose of political society. The Right to Life and the Right to Fair Hearing (often expressed as the right to a fair trial) represent the moral and legal essence of this framework. They are fundamental principles of international law that cannot be violated, even in times of national emergency. (Cassese, 2005; Nickel, 2007). Consequently, states have both negative obligations (to refrain from violating rights) and positive obligations (to protect individuals from harm by others).

In the Nigerian context, this theoretical framework offers a lens for assessing the moral and legal adequacy of state institutions in fulfilling their human rights obligations. Nigeria's constitutional and institutional architecture derives much of its normative legitimacy from these universal human rights principles, yet the persistence of violations particularly in the South-East reveals a significant disjunction between theory and practice. Human Rights Theory thus provides a normative benchmark for evaluating this discrepancy and for analyzing the role of external actors such as the United Nations in bridging the compliance gap.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study is qualitative in orientation and therefore adopted Descriptive Research Design. The researcher generated data from secondary sources, including textbooks, journal articles, and various documented or published evidence. Specifically, the study reviewed reports, publications, and case records from domestic institutions, such as the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), Nigerian Correctional Services, the National Commission for Administration of Justice (NCAT), and the Federal Civil Investigation Bureau (FCIB).

DATA ANALYSIS

Human Rights Abuses in South-East Nigeria and United Nations Interventions (2015–2023)

Since the return to democratic governance in 1999, Nigeria has sought to institutionalize the protection and promotion of human rights. The 1999 Constitution (as amended) guarantees fundamental rights, including the **Right to Life (Section 33)** and the **Right to Fair Hearing (Section 36)**. Internationally, Nigeria is a signatory to instruments such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966) and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (1981), reflecting formal commitment to global human rights standards.

Despite these frameworks, violations persist in South-East Nigeria, particularly due to separatist movements, political unrest, and security operations. Reports from the NHRC, UNHRC, and Amnesty International indicate ongoing challenges including extrajudicial killings, arbitrary arrests, torture, prolonged detention, and denial of fair hearing rights (Amnesty International, 2022; NHRC, 2020; UNHRC, 2021). This chapter analyzes the patterns of violations, the role of the United Nations through mechanisms like the UPR, domestic institutional capacity, challenges to enforcement, and strategies for strengthening human rights protection. The analysis is guided by Human Rights Theory, emphasizing the interplay between universal human rights norms and domestic capacity.

Nature and Patterns of Human Rights Violations

Human rights violations in South-East Nigeria between 2015 and 2023 have been extensive, systematic, and multifaceted. Despite formal guarantees in both the Nigerian Constitution and international human rights instruments, the lived reality for many residents has been one of insecurity, arbitrary deprivation of liberty, and denial of access to justice. These violations have occurred in the context of a tense political environment marked by separatist agitations, civil unrest, and a securitized state response to perceived threats. The activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and the Nigerian security forces have created a dynamic in which both civilian populations and activists are frequently caught between state action and non-state insurgency activities (Amnesty International, 2022; Human Rights Watch, 2021). Many lives have equally been lost and properties destroyed.

Extrajudicial Killings and Use of Excessive Force

Extrajudicial killings have been a defining feature of human rights abuses in the South-East during the period under study. These killings often occur during security operations against separatist groups, as well as during civil protests. Amnesty International (2022) and NHRC (2021) report numerous cases where security operatives used lethal force without due process, resulting in the deaths of both suspected insurgents and bystanders. The use of force is frequently disproportionate to the threat posed, reflecting a culture of impunity among security personnel and a lack of accountability mechanisms. Such killings not only violate the constitutional Right to Life (Section 33, 1999 Constitution) but also compromise the broader security of civilian populations, fostering distrust in state institutions.

Case illustrations, such as the 2015 clashes in Anambra and Imo States, underscore the pattern of killings during operations targeting IPOB activities. Victims often include young men and community leaders whose detention or elimination occurs without formal charges or judicial review. These incidents reveal systemic weaknesses in law enforcement and highlight the failure of state institutions to reconcile security objectives with human rights obligations.

Denial of Fair Trial and Judicial Inefficiencies

The South-East's judicial system has struggled to uphold the Right to Fair Trial. Challenges include delayed hearings, executive interference, inconsistent application of legal procedures, and limited independence of the judiciary (NHRC, 2022; Adebisi, Oyedeji, & Azeez, 2016). Victims of arbitrary detention or security crackdowns frequently face restricted access to legal representation, prolonged

pre-trial detention, and obstruction of habeas corpus petitions. These systemic inefficiencies erode the credibility of the judiciary as a protector of fundamental rights.

High-profile cases, such as that of Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, exemplify the intersection of political sensitivity, judicial inadequacy, and human rights violations. Kanu's detention, contested extradition, and restricted access to counsel illustrate the structural vulnerabilities within both judicial and security systems and the failure to operationalize constitutional protections in practice.

United Nations Interventions through the Universal Periodic Review (UPR) and Human Rights Compliance in South-East Nigeria

The **Universal Periodic Review (UPR)** is a peer-review mechanism established by the United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC) in 2006 to assess the human rights records of all UN member states. Operating on the principle of cooperative dialogue, the UPR seeks to improve domestic human rights practices, fulfill international obligations, and promote accountability without resorting to punitive international sanctions (Smith, 2018). Nigeria has participated in four UPR cycles: 2009, 2013, 2018, and 2023, each reflecting evolving challenges across the federation, particularly in politically volatile regions such as South-East Nigeria.

Contextualizing UPR in South-East Nigeria

South-East Nigeria comprising Anambra, Enugu, Imo, Abia, and Ebonyi States has experienced intensified human rights concerns, particularly between 2015 and 2023. The resurgence of IPOB activism, frequent civil protests, and high-profile security operations drew heightened international scrutiny during UPR cycles. The UPR provides an institutional framework through which local violations can be highlighted, recommendations issued, and accountability promoted.

Empirical observations indicate that UPR recommendations addressing the **Right to Life** and the **Right to Fair Hearing** have been especially pertinent in the South-East. Recommendations consistently focused on curbing extrajudicial killings, ensuring judicial independence, improving access to legal representation, protecting human rights defenders, and strengthening law enforcement oversight. Despite these prescriptions, implementation at the state level has been uneven, particularly in areas of political tension and active separatist movements (Emelonye, 2021; NHRC, 2020).

Implications for Human Rights Compliance

The South-East experience underscores that the UPR, while a critical normative tool, cannot function in isolation. Its effectiveness depends on:

- **Autonomy and capacity of domestic institutions** (NHRC, NCAT, judiciary)
- **Political will** to implement recommendations at state and local levels
- **Public awareness and civil society engagement** to monitor enforcement
- **Security and socio-political stability**, which affect feasibility of rights-based reforms

Analysis indicates that while the UPR has increased international attention and normative pressure, compliance with recommendations particularly regarding the Right to Life and Right to Fair Hearing remains partial. Sustainable protection of these rights requires a synergistic approach combining UN oversight, domestic institutional strengthening, political accountability, and active civil society participation.

CONCLUSION

The study reveal that United Nations has significantly contributed to raising awareness and promoting discourse on human rights in South-East Nigeria, the tangible outcomes of its interventions remain limited. Persistent Human Rights Violations Despite International Engagement. Weak Institutional Enforcement and Capacity Deficits. Low Implementation of UPR Recommendations. Security-Oriented Governance and Rights Abuses. Fragmented UN–Civil Society Partnerships. Partial Effectiveness of UN Interventions.

The study concludes that while the United Nations has made commendable efforts to promote human rights in South-East Nigeria, its influence has been primarily normative rather than transformative. The persistence of violations of the Right to Life and the Right to Fair Trial underscores the limitations of international engagement in contexts where domestic institutions are weak and political will is low.

RECOMMENDATION

Amongst the recommendations is that sustainable human rights improvement in South-East Nigeria will depend on strengthened judicial independence, empowered national institutions such as the NHRC and NCAT, and transparent oversight of security agencies. Active civil society participation and continuous engagement with international partners are vital to sustaining reform momentum. Achieving durable progress requires collective action by state institutions, civil society, and citizens to institutionalize the principles of justice, equality, and respect for human dignity in both law and practice.

REFERENCES

- Abangwu, N. E. & Imosemi, A. (2019). Progressive enforcement of international human rights norms in Nigeria: the question of access to justice. *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6 (9), pp. 397-408. Retrieved from https://ijiset.com/vol6/v6s9/IJSET_V6_I9_33.pdf on October 12, 2023
- Abbott, K. W., & Snidal, D. (1998). Why states act through formal international organizations. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 42(1), 3–32.
- Achebe, C. (1983). *The trouble with Nigeria*. Town: Heinemann.
- Achebe, C. (2012).** *There Was a Country: A Personal History of Biafra*. Town: Penguin Books.
- Adebisi, M., Oyediji, T., & Azeez, A. (2016). *Human rights and democratic governance in Nigeria*. Lagos: Spectrum Books.
- Adebisi, S., Oyediji, R. & Azeez, O. (2016). Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. Defining, addressing and understanding its impact on telecommunication industry. *Economics and Management Research Project: Open Access International Journal*, 5 (1), pp. 1-8. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/2045/49ed1160da91fd61baec693af2do3acb5615pdf> on September 18, 2023
- Blessing Chugo Idigo (2024). Cross Border Migration and Human Security in Nigeria: Journal of Education, Humanities, Management & Social Sciences (JEHMSS), September 2024
- Dominguez-Redondo, E. (2010). The role of the UN in the protection of human rights. *Middlesex University, London*. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/693246/Role_of_the_UN_in_the_Promotion_and_Protection_of_Human_Rights_An_Introduction_to_International_Human-Rights_Law_Rahman_Chowdhury_and_Hossain_Bhuiyan_eds_Martinus_Nij_Publishers_2010_119_114 on August 24, 2023
- Haruna, B. A., & Yusuf, A. M. (2017). A conceptual analysis of the rule of law in Nigeria. *Bayero Journal of International Law & Jurisprudence*, 7(2), 101-127. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321017220> on February 20, 2024
- Human Rights Watch. (2022). *Nigeria: Excessive use of force and unlawful killings by security forces*. New York: HRW Publications.
- Human Rights Watch. (2022). *World Report 2022: Nigeria*. Retrieved from Human Rights Watch
- Human Rights Watch. (2023). *Human rights abuses in Nigeria: The security forces and beyond*. Human Rights Watch.
- Idigo, B.C (2025). African union, conflict resolution and Malian conflict: Multidisciplinary Research And Development Journal INT'L 7(1)2-23
- Idigo, B.C. (2022) Terrorism and national security in Nigeria: A case of Boko-Haram, 2019-2022. *International journal of general studies*, 2(1), pp. 86-104
- Idigo, B.C. (2024). Cross border migration and human security in Nigeria. *Journal of Education, Humanities, Management & Social Sciences, (JEHMSS)*, 2(4), pp. 37-60 www.journalonline.com
- Idigo, B.C (2024). Bureaucratic Corruption and Socio-Economic Development in Nigeria: A Study of Buhari Administration: *International Journal of Innovative Legal & Political Studies* 12(4):39-52
- Idigo, B.C (2024). Effect of China-Nigeria Economic Relations on Infrastructural Development in Nigeria: *International Journal of Innovative Legal & Political Studies* 12(1):11-25,
- Ki-moon, B. (2015). *Universal declaration of human rights*. New York

- Kirchschlaeger, P. G. (2014). The relation between democracy and human rights. *Globalistics and Globalization Studies*, pp. 112-125. Retrieved from https://www.sociostudies.org/books/files/globalistics_and_globalization_studies_3/112-125.pdf on November 17, 2023
- Kuijer, M. (2014). Effective remedies as a fundamental right. In E. Brems (Ed.), *Human rights and civil liberties in the 21st century* (pp. 91-106). Heidelberg, Germany: Springer.
- Obiora, C. A. (2021). International cooperation and human rights institutions in Nigeria. *African Journal of Peace and Development Studies*, 6(2), 55–72.
- Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). (1993). *Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action*. New York, NY: United Nations.
- Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). (2010). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights at 60: Human rights in the public eye*. New York, NY: United Nations Publications.
- Ofoegbu, J. U. (2013). The place of human rights in Nigeria’s democracy. *Journal of Asian Studies*, 10 (1), pp. 60-79. Retrieved from www.researchgate.net on September 29, 2023
- Ofoegbu, R. (2013). *Human rights, law and justice in Nigeria*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers.
- Ohaeri, V. (2020). *Human rights, governance, and reform in post-Biafra Nigeria*. Lagos: Spaces for Change Publications.
- Ojo, E. O. (2017). Human rights institutions and the rule of law in Nigeria’s Fourth Republic. *African Journal of Legal Studies*, 10(3), 170–193.
- Ojukwu, C. (2022). *Human rights and institutional accountability in Nigeria’s South-East*. Enugu: Institute for Development Studies.
- Ojukwu, C. (2022). United Nations interventions and human rights protection in South-East Nigeria. *Journal of International Relations and Diplomacy*, 12(1), 85–106.
- Okafor, O. (2014). *Reconstructing post-conflict societies: Lessons from Nigeria’s South-East region*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.
- Risse, T., Ropp, S. C., & Sikkink, K. (1999). *The Power of Human Rights: International Norms and Domestic Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Robinson, M. (n.d.). *Statement on Justice and Human Rights*. United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights.
- Rosenblatt, J. (2000). Human rights and state responsibilities. *World Affairs Journal*, 162(1), 18–25.
- Rosenblatt, N. M. (2000). The right to life and the prohibition against torture and inhuman or degrading treatment. In R. Burchill, N. D. White, & J. Morris (Eds.), *International conflict and security law: Essays in memory of Hilaire McCoubrey* (pp. 108-123). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Roth, K. (2004). *Defending economic, social, and cultural rights: Practical dilemmas and strategic choices*. Human Rights Watch.
- Ruggie, J. G. (1992). Multilateralism: The anatomy of an institution. *International Organization*, 46(3), 561–598.
- UN Women. (2021). *Civil society engagement in the Commission on the Status of Women*. New York, NY: United Nations.
- UN Women. (2023). *Gender inequality in Nigeria: A persistent problem*. UN Women Reports.
- UNDP. (2007). *Judicial reform and capacity building in Nigeria*. New York: United Nations Development Programme.
- UNDP. (2021). *Socio-economic disparities in Nigeria: Regional imbalances and human rights*. United Nations Development Programme.
- UNDP. (2021). *Strengthening human rights systems in Nigeria*. Abuja: United Nations Development Programme.
- UNDP. (2022). *Human rights-based approach to development programming*. Geneva: United Nations Development Programme.
- United Nations Development Programme. (2022). *Youth Empowerment and Human Rights in Nigeria*. Retrieved from UNDP
- United Nations Economic and Social Council (2008). What is ECOSOC. Retrieved from https://www.un.org/en/ecosoc/docs/pdfs/ecosoc_brochure_en.pdf on September 22, 2023

- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2021). *Education and Human Rights in Nigeria*. Retrieved from UNESCO
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2021). *Cultural Rights and Heritage Protection in Nigeria*. Retrieved from UNESCO
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2020). *Environmental Rights and Human Health in Nigeria*. Retrieved from UNEP
- United Nations Foundation (2018, December 6). 70 years of impact: insights on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Retrieved from <https://unfoundation.org/blog/post/70-years-of-impact-insights-on-the-universal-declaration-of-human-rights/> on December 2, 2023
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). (2017). *Support to the justice sector in Nigeria: Enhancing institutional capacity and human rights protection*. UNODC.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). (2017). *Support to the justice sector in Nigeria*. Vienna: UNODC.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). (2022). *Implementation of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption (UNCAC) in Nigeria*. UNODC.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2019). *Support to justice sector reform in Nigeria (2015–2019): Final report*. Vienna: UNODC.
- United Nations. (2007). *United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (A/RES/61/295)*. New York, NY: United Nations General Assembly.
- United Nations. (2019). *Human Rights Committee report (CCPR/C/127/1)*. New York, NY: United Nations.
- United Nations. (2020). *Human Rights Treaty Bodies' follow-up procedures*. Retrieved from OHCHR website
- United Nations. (2020). *The role of civil society in the United Nations system*. United Nations.
- United Nations. (2021). *Individual complaints mechanisms under the human rights treaties*. Retrieved from OHCHR website
- United Nations. (2023). *General Assembly Third Committee resolutions*. Retrieved from United Nations website
- United Nations. (2024). *Collaboration between UN and Nigeria to address internal displacement: A comprehensive strategy for durable solutions*. United Nations.
- United Nations' Office of the High Commissioner (n.d). Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Webpage. Retrieved from <https://www.ohchr.org/en/universal-declaration-of-human-rights> on December 14, 2023
- UPR. (2021). *Nigeria and the UPR: Review statistics*. United Nations Human Rights Council.
- Urquhart (1988, July 16). Looking for Sheriff. New York Review of Books. Retrieved from <https://www.nybooks.com/articles/1998/07/16/looking-for-the-sheriff/> on August 16, 2023
- Zalta, E. N. (2012). *The Stanford encyclopedia of philosophy* (Fall 2012 ed.). Stanford, CA: Stanford University.
- Zenn, J. (2014). *Boko Haram and the Threat to Nigeria's Stability*. Terrorism Monitor, 12(4), 10-12.